

ERRATUM

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Erratum to: Formal ontologies and strategic environmental assessment. A case study: the municipal land use plan of Genoa

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In the publication of this article (Lombardini 2016), the following acknowledgment failed to be included:

‘This article is the outcome of a research project coordinated by Prof. M. Besio, Department of Sciences for Architecture, Genoa-I. The research aimed to develop a strategic environmental assessment for the Municipality of Genoa, Italy. All images were produced by the Municipality of Genoa-UrbaLab, Silvia Capurro, Anna Mara Colombo and Cristina Giusso. The author has acquired permission to include them in the article.’

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